

Flavonoids of *Zizyphus* species

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Abstract : 7-Methoxyflavone and quercetin from *Zizyphus mauritiana* and kaempferol-4'-methylether and kaempferol from *Zizyphus xylopyra* has been isolated from their root barks and their structures established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these flavonoids from these plants.

Keywords : Flavonoids, quercetin, kaempferol.

Zizyphus mauritiana Lam.¹ and *Zizyphus xylopyra* Willd.² (Rhamnaceae) are distributed throughout India. *Z. mauritiana* is used in Indian System of Medicine for the treatment of ulcers, stomach diseases, fever and eye complaints¹. However, isolation of flavonoids from *Z. xylopyra* has not been reported earlier, which may find medicinal uses. Here, we report the isolation and characterisation of two flavonoids from *Z. mauritiana* and two flavonoids from *Z. xylopyra* from their root barks.

Experimental

Root barks of the plants *Z. mauritiana* and *Z. xylopyra* were collected from Mirzapur District, U.P., India. The root barks of *Z. mauritiana* were dried, powdered and extracted with MeOH in a Soxhlet extractor. The MeOH extract was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluants collected from C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1 : 9) and CHCl₃ on crystallisation from MeOH furnished respectively 7-methoxyflavone³ (1), as yellowish amorphous powder (20 mg) and quercetin⁴ (2) as yellow granules (22 mg), m.p. 310-312 °C.

Dried powdered root barks of *Z. xylopyra* were extracted with MeOH as above and chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column. The eluants collected from C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1 : 4) and CHCl₃ on crystallisation from MeOH furnished respectively, kaempferol-4'-methylether⁵ (3) as yellow granules (36 mg), m.p. 224-226 °C and kaempferols⁵ (4) as yellow granules (22 mg), m.p. 270-273 °C.

The spectral data of the above mentioned compounds

are given below :

Compound 1 : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} 252, 272, 309 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 2790 (Ar-OCH₃), 1660 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.75 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.85 (1H, s, H-3), 6.93 (1H, complex, H-4'), 7.00 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.58 (3H, complex, H-6, H-3', H-5'), 7.90 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5), 8.02 (2H, complex, H-2', H-6'); 100 MHz ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 162.4 (C-2), 102.2 (C-3), 176.0 (C-4), 131.2 (C-5), 116.2 (C-6), 161.7 (C-7), 106.4 (C-8), 157.2 (C-9), 115.0 (C-10), 126.5 (C-1'), 126.2 (C-2'), 129.0 (C-3'), 131.2 (C-4'), 129.0 (C-5'), 126.2 (C-6'), 56.0 (-OCH₃); MS, *m/z* 252.0786 (M⁺, C₁₆H₁₂O₃), 224, 223, 150, 122, 102.

Compound 2 : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} 256, 270 sh, 300 sh, 370 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3100-3500 (-OH), 1650, 1630 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.22 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.24 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-2'), 7.29 (1H, dd, *J* 2 and 9 Hz, H-6'), 12.50 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH); MS, *m/z* 302 (M⁺, C₁₅H₁₀O₇), 274, 152, 150, 124.

Compound 3 : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} 256, 368 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3200-3600 (-OH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.85 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.38 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.11 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.50 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH), 10.14 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O,

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-OH), 12.40 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH); MS, *m/z* 300 (M⁺, C₁₆H₁₂O₆), 272, 257, 229, 152, 148, 124.

Compound 4 : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} 269, 308 sh, 360 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3320 (-OH), 1665, 1620 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6), 6.44 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8), 6.94 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.08 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.44 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH), 10.14 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH), 10.84 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH), 12.54 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, -OH); MS, *m/z* 286 (M⁺, C₁₅H₁₀O₆), 258, 257, 152, 134, 124.

The structures of all the above compounds were

supported by a study of the UV with shift reagents and direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

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